

Formulation and *in vitro* evaluation of Donepezil hydrochloride rapid dissolving oral thin film

Keshireddy Anji Reddy and S. Karpagam*

Organic Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : skarpagam80@yahoo.com

Abstract : The present work was aimed to formulate Donepezil hydrochloride fast dissolving oral thin films (OTF) which is certainly useful for the elderly patients. Solvent casting technique is employed to formulate Donepezil hydrochloride oral thin films, HPMC and PEG-400 were used as film forming polymers. Two formulations F1 and F2 were prepared by changing the polymer and drug ratio. The physical characteristics was evaluated such as folding endurance, weight variation, thickness, drug content, disintegration time, drug release and gave satisfactory results. From the atomic force microscopy (3D-AFM), the surface roughness was found to be 54.17 nm. The drug and polymer compatibility study was carried out by FTIR, particle size of film was evaluated by optical microscopy. Fast dissolving OTF containing HPMC showed optimum performance against pure drug and marketed formulations. F2 formulation showed slightly higher cumulative % drug release i.e. 90% in 2 h compared to pure drug (50%) and marketed formulation (70%). From the results, rate of dissolution was increased in HPMC formulated OTF and this is therapeutically effective against Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords : Oral thin film, solvent casting, *in vitro*, AFM, HPMC, Donepezil.

Introduction

Oral disintegrating drug delivery system was first developed in the late 1970, especially for geriatric patients who had difficulties in swallowing conventional dosage forms¹. Oral disintegrating tablet (ODT) is an example for oral drug delivery. This is placed on the mouth which is allowed to disperse and dissolved in the saliva before it enters into stomach². Oral disintegrating film (ODF) is different from ODT, film containing hydrophilic polymer which will readily absorb saliva and dissolves rapidly in the mouth itself³. Film posses larger surface area which dissolves film effectively, ease of administration it gives better patient compliance⁴. Donepezil is characteristically bitter in taste⁶. Most of the elderly patients are facing trouble in swallowing commercial dosage forms like tablets and capsule⁷. Therefore, to deal even less cooperative patients⁸, administration of dosage form is placed vital role especially in Alzheimer's disease.

Generally Donepezil hydrochloride is used to treat the symptoms of dementia in people diagnosed with severe Alzheimer's disease⁹. Enzyme acetyl cholinesterase acts as reversible inhibitor for Donepezil hydrochloride.

As increasing the concentration of acetyl cholinesterase, the therapeutic effect of drug also increases due to hydrolysis of acetyl cholinesterase through reversible inhibition. The objective of the present study was to implement solvent casting technique to prepare oral thin film (OTF) of Donepezil by solvent casting method using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) and poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) polymers. Physical properties and surface morphology of the film was measured, cumulative % drug release characteristics were carried out by using *in vitro* dissolution studies.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Donepezil hydrochloride was received from Natco Pharma Ltd., Hyderabad (India). HPMC 3Cps grade, poly ethylene glycol-400, glycerin and citric acid were purchased from NICE Chemicals (Chennai, India).

Preparation of oral thin film :

Generally solvent-casting technique is used for preparing oral disintegrating film, firstly HPMC, citric acid and glycerol was dissolved in water to attain the clear

solution. Then drug was added and allowed to stir for 1 h (1500 rpm). Simultaneously PEG-400 was dissolved and allowed to stir for 30 min. These two solutions were mixed and stirred for 2 h. Mixed solution was sonicated for 15 min to remove air bubbles; finally solution was poured into petri dish and allowed to dry at 40 °C for 6 h in a hot air oven. Film was taken carefully from petri dish and cut the film as per requirements for various characterizations.

Physical characteristics of oral thin film :

Thickness :

Thickness of each film was measured with calibrated screw gauge and vernier caliper at different location of film which was measured to ensure uniformity of film thickness¹¹.

Weight of film :

Same size 1 × 1 cm² of the film was cut at different areas from the casted film and average weight was found¹².

Folding endurance :

Film was subjected to be folded repeatedly at same place until it gets breaks. The number of folding was calculated for folding endurance¹³.

Drug content :

Drug content was estimated from UV-spectroscopy. 4 cm² of film was allowed to keep in 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 6.8) by taking absorbance of filtered solution at 230 nm and drug content was calculated by considering standard curve of the drug¹⁴.

Surface pH measurement :

Film was allowed to get in contact with water to check pH reading and performed in triplicate. It was used to find out possible side effects under neutral medium.

Appearance of films :

Physical appearance of film was generally visible with naked eye and films were examined for color, stickiness property and presence of cracks¹⁵.

In vitro disintegration test :

Film was placed in petri dish containing 25 ml of buffer solution (pH 6.8) at 37 ± 5 °C and swirled at interval of 10 s. Readings were taken in an average of three¹⁶.

In vitro dissolution test :

Oral thin film of Donepezil thin films were carried

out by using USP dissolution apparatus I basket type by taking 900 ml of pH 6.8 buffer solution. Setting 50 rpm at a temperature of 37 ± 5 °C maintained. Each time 5 ml of sample withdrawn from medium as per predetermined sample intervals this was replaced with fresh medium. Samples were diluted and assayed by UV-spectroscopy at 230 nm. Studies were conducted in triplicate.

Results and discussion

Solvent casting technique was used for the formulation of different oral thin films F1 and F2, HPMC and PEG was used as film-forming agents. Glycerol used as plasticizer and citric acid used as saliva stimulating agent. The ingredients of two formulations (F1, F2) are listed in Table 1. From the table, the two different ratios of HPMC and drug were used to study the drug release pattern.

Table 1. Formula

Ingredients	F1	F2
Drug	5 mg	5 mg
HPMC 3cps	40 mg	45 mg
PEG-400	15 ml	10 ml
Citric acid	3 mg	3 mg
Glycerol	1 ml	1 ml
Distilled water	15 ml	15 ml

Various physical properties are shown in Table 2. The parameters were varied from F1 to F2 based on HPMC concentration. The obtained results were shown the smooth appearance of film, good folding endurance and also confirmed that the drug was distributed uniformly in both formulations on thin film.

Fourier Transform Infrared study (FTIR) :

The drug and polymer compatibility was performed by using FT-IR studies. The structural characteristics of thin film, polymer and drug were presented in Fig. 1. The aromatic phenone and hydrocarbons are major functional groups in the drug. This was clearly observed in OTF which formed at 1649.14 cm⁻¹ and 2843.07 cm⁻¹. The sharp absorption peak formed at 1323.17 cm⁻¹ which represents the C-N stretching in the structure. This was proved that represented functional groups were present in the ODF formulated compound. This is also proved that there is no chemical interaction between Donepezil hydrochloride and HPMC in ODF formulation.

Table 2. Physical evaluation of film

Form	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug content (%)	Surface pH	Weight of film (mg)	Appearance	Disintegration time (min)
F1	0.22 ± 0.5	55.58 ± 1.07	94.11 ± 1.01	6.8 ± 0.45	20.58 ± 1.07	Translucent	95 ± 0.5
F2	0.22 ± 0.5	60.45 ± 1.04	90.02 ± 0.30	6.9 ± 0.05	21.45 ± 1.24	Slightly yellow	90 ± 0.49

Results in parentheses shows SD, n = 3.

Fig. 1. FT-IR results of thin film, drug and polymer.

Optical microscopy :

Arrangement of the particles may be observed from optical microscopy which is shown in Fig. 2. From the images F1 and F2 thin films, needle shaped particle was observed. The results are appearing of clear image of thin film.

Fig. 2. Optical microscopy images of thin films.

Surface morphology (AFM) :

The 3D atomic force microscopy (AFM) study of films F1 and F2 are presented in Fig. 3 which gives topographic image of the surface. OTF surface is allowed to detect roughness parameters. Surfaces were imaged in tapping mode minimum of five scans by covering different areas of film. From the image, the roughness average (Sa) of F1 was observed as 33.158 nm and F2 was observed as 54.17 nm. The surface roughness was highly influenced by the drug releasing pattern of ODF¹⁰.

Fig. 3. AFM-images of films (a) F1, (b) F2.

In vitro dissolution studies :

Dissolution studies of thin films (F1, F2) marketed drug and pure drug are shown in Fig. 4. From the graph, F2 formulation was showed good cumulative % drug release which was 90% in 2 h than F1 formulation (86% drug release). This was highly correlated with AFM spectroscopy. More surface roughness of F2 formulation has more efficiency of releasing the drug than F1 formulation. Results also explains, HPMC formulated ODF (F1, F2) showed slightly higher cumulative % drug release compared to pure drug (50%) and marketed formulation (70%).

Fig. 4. Comparative dissolutions studies of ODF, pure drug and marketed tablet.

Conclusion

Prepared Donepezil hydrochloride film was showed better drug dissolution results compared to pure drug and marketed sample. Film was given satisfactory results in

all evaluation parameters like disintegration time, thickness and drug content. Film evaluated for Optical microscopy study, roughness parameters by considering 3D AFM studies.

Acknowledgement

We thank VIT University for providing laboratory facilities, SIF and Nanotechnology Lab for recording instrumental characterization.

References

1. H. Sunada and Y. X. Bi, *Powder Technol.*, 2002, **122**, 188.
2. G. Abdelbary, C. Eouani, P. Prinderre and J. Joachim, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2005, **292**, 29.
3. R. P. Dixit and S. P. Puthli, *J. Control Release*, 2009, **139**, 94.
4. H. Goel, P. Rai, V. Rana and A. K. Tiwary, *Recent Patents on Drug Delivery and Formulation*, 2008, **2**, 258.
5. R. F. Martin, *Am. J. Med.*, 2007, **120**, 388.
6. T. Hanawa, *J. Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 1997, **13**, 251.
7. Y. Yamamoto, M. Fujii, K. Watanabe, M. Tsukamoto, Y. Shibata and M. Kondoh, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2009, **365**, 116.
8. T. D. Joseph, L. T. Robert, C. Y. Gary, G. W. Barbara and L. P. Michael, *Am. Ass. Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 2012, **13**, 134.
9. K. B. Liew, Y. T. Fungtan and K. K. Peh, *AAPS Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 2012, 134.
10. G. Royall, M. Q. Craig and M. Price, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1999, **192**, 97.
11. N. Sapkal, V. Kilor and A. Daud, *J. Arch. Plan. Res.*, 2011, **2**, 102.
12. B. Bhupinder and J. Sarita, *Int. J. Drug. Delivery*, 2012, **4**, 133.
13. A. J. Shinde, K. C. Garala and H. N. More, *Asian J. Pharm.*, 2008, **2**, 265.
14. R. Patel, N. Shardul, J. Patel and A. Baria, *Arch. Pharm. Sci. & Res.*, 2009, **1**, 212.
15. A. Jyoti, S. Gurpreet, S. Seema, A. C. Rana and M. Pooja, *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2012, **4**, 1739; M. D. Siddiqui, G. Garg and P. Sharma, *Adv. Bio. Res.*, 2011, **5**, 291.